

**EPIDEMIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE SPREAD OF ACUTE
INTESTINAL DISEASES IN UZBEKISTAN**

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Resume

This article provides information on the global prevalence of acute diarrheal diseases and the occurrence characteristics of causative agents of diarrheal diseases, as well as the condition in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: diarrhea, causative agent, salmonellosis, dysentery, virus.

Since diarrheal diseases are among the common, common, and at the same time causing enormous economic damage in our country, kurrai is also in the spotlight of scientists all over the world. As a result of the severe and persistent course of this disease in humans, especially in children, a significant increase in mortality among them is an impetus for the inexhaustible research of specialists in the relevant field.

It should be noted that these diseases not only lead to large economic losses in the premature death of children, but also a certain blow to the foundation of the formation of a healthy generation, which is reflected in the mental and physical development of the child: the child becomes capricious, indifferent and weak, as a result of which he is prone to various superstitions and ailments, causing.

Also, as a result of diarrheal diseases, the basis is also laid for the formation of a number of chronic somatic diseases (for example, gastritis, enteritis, enterocolitis, colitis, etc.), which ultimately leads to the fact that the person in question will suffer or remain disabled for a lifetime.

According to the Jaxon Health Organization's definition, diarrhea, i.e. diarrhea, is one of the symptoms of most pathological conditions, which is constipation in the form of liquid feces (enough to take the form of a poured container) three or more times over a 24 - hour period. The main diseases of this sign are referred to as diarrheal diseases.

The results of research conducted by Jaxon Health Organization and other foreign scientists show that in the countries of Asia, Africa and Latin America, aged children under 5 years of age suffer about 1 billion with ulcers (acute infectious intestinal diseases), of which 4.6 million. as long as the dead end. In recent years, as a result of the rise of medical science and the improvement of treatment methods, cases of recovery from the disease have increased, and the death rate in this regard is 3.3 million.down to.

A characteristic for all regions is that escherichioses are mainly (in the case of 3/4 parts) common among the population living in the city. The main reasons for this are that, firstly, there are many conditions for triggers to call disease in the city, and

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secondly, Bacteriological Methods of diagnosis are well established in the city. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the incidence of oysters is much higher, with a trend of decline in recent years. These indicators are especially high among children, and there is no tendency to decrease the severity of the disease.

It is worth noting that in the USA there are more and more cases of pain with salmonellosis. Research shows that the holos, while only 1-5% of cases of real salmonellez are officially taken into account during the year. There are also growing cases of salmonellese pain in the UK. The largest foci of salmonellez incidence in RF range from 53-115 people per Flash, to 162 people, mostly kindergartens, with incidence observed. The instigators were mainly salmonelle of the D guru. Dysentery, on the other hand, decreased by 36% in 2000 compared to previous years. Similar rates have occurred in the Republic of Uzbekistan, in the regions of chunonchi Samarkand, Andijan, Tashkent in 1990, the incidence per 100,000 inhabitants fell from 20-40, while in 2000 it decreased to 15-18. According to reports, the incidence of dysentery in the Khorezm region was 37 per 100,000 inhabitants in 1991, compared to 3.2 by 2015. According to the Ministry of health of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in the Khorezm region in 1992, 709.9 cases of acute intestinal infections per 100,000 inhabitants were registered, which means 1.4 times more than the average of our country.

The positive state of Health and sanitation of children, in turn, is closely related to the decrease in the level of infectious diseases in our country. When studying the causes of infectious diseases and an increase in the mortality of children, as well as developing practical recommendations for their reduction, it is important to take into account all factors in the health of the population, including the level of environmental pollution, since the children's organism is especially susceptible to the level of environmental pollution. The development and distribution of grooves among humans initially depends on the socio-economic development of society, the lifestyle of the population, as well as the type, quantity and virulence of triggers.

Along with the changes that have taken place in our Mother Nature over the centuries, including ecological disturbances, an evolutionary process has also occurred in the triggers of infectious diseases, in particular, ulcers. The pathogenicity and virulence properties of infectious disease pathogens under the influence of colorful external and internal factors are in the variable. To date, many pathogenic microorganisms have disappeared, replaced by new species that have not been encountered before and are now adapted to the conditions of the modern environment. Therefore, it is especially important to identify the triggers of OIC lari, to assess their importance holistically, to diagnose, therapy and prophylaxis of these diseases.

The ecologically unfavorable conditions caused by the drying of the Aral Sea have

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severely adversely affected the flora, fauna and climate of the region. The population living in the same region is especially manifested by the deterioration in the health of women of childbearing age, which is a sensitive part of it, an increase in the number of cases. In our opinion, environmentally unfavorable conditions not only negatively affect the world of Man, animals and plants, but also change the properties of microorganisms. Over the past years, the clinical course of infectious diseases, in particular intestinal infections, and the epidemic process in them have changed radically. That is why their etiological diagnosis does not cause significant complications. In recent times, a somewhat mild course of most ulcers, severe forms and a decrease in intoxication, a significant decrease in relapses and lethal States, while changes in the characteristics of disease triggers also necessitate the need to dwell separately on the features of the occurrence of OIC Lar triggers.

We can also cite Salmonella, Shigella, Iersinae, Proteus Campylobacter and other microorganisms as triggers that cause ulcers in other countries of Central Asia and in Kazakhstan.

The Shigella are divided into three regions based on their degree of distribution: the first is Sh.the sonnei trigger is the region that calls for more disease; the second is Sh.flexneri ET Co.sonnei is a region of diseases that serve as the same etiological factor; the third is Sh.flexneri is a common region. It should be noted that our country is part of the third region. In addition to bacteria and simple animals, viruses, chunonchi, rotaviruses can also be cited as one of the causes of diarrheal diseases: in the RF during 1997-2001, the number of patients with rotavirus infection increased by 2 barovars compared to previous years. More than 70% of patients were identified during the cold season of the year, while 91% of cases occurred among children. Descendants of intestinal adenoviruses, enteroviruses and other similar viruses may also play a role in human OIC etiology in some cases.

Conclusion. As can be seen from the etiology of oysters, the causative agents of these diseases are diverse, the socio-economic, climatic-geographical conditions of their origin, as well as the age of the infected, the condition and living conditions of their organism are important.

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